

Observations on the pale ground spiders of *Eleleis limpopo* (Araneae: Prodidomidae)

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ABSTRACT: The pale ground spiders of the genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893 are known from nine species endemic to Africa. They are shy and small ground-dwelling spiders and very little is known about their behaviour. One of the species, *Eleleis limpopo* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020, was sampled from several localities in South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893, represented by nine species, is known from Botswana, Cape Verde, Namibia, South Africa and Zambia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). Prior to the revision of Rodrigues and Rheims (2020), *Eleleis* was only known from the type species *Eleleis crinita* Simon, 1893. In their revision, they recognised eight new *Eleleis* species, of which four are known from South Africa.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), spiders were sampled throughout the country Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). During the SANSa Gauteng surveys, the second author (PW) regularly sampled one of these small spiders that are now identified as *Eleleis limpopo*.

The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. A series of photographs were taken by PW from several localities in Gauteng.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Eleleis belongs to the Prodidominae and this subfamily was transferred from Prodidomidae to Gnaphosidae by Azevedo *et al.* (2018); however, in a new paper, Azevedo *et al.* (2022) again recognised the family rank Prodidomidae. Species of *Eleleis* are distinguished from other Prodidomidae genera by the presence of different sized clavate setae over the entire body, except the chelicerae and spinnerets.

Eleleis limpopo Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Eleleis limpopo Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020: 19–27.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL 1.72–3.90 mm. Carapace bears a few long and oblique clavate setae (Figs 1 & 3); posterior eye row is strongly procurved and anterior eye row approximately straight; posterior median eyes and posterior lateral eyes irregular; anterior median eyes dark (Figs 2 & 8). Sternum heart shaped (Fig. 7). Abdomen ovoid, with posterior region bearing large and robust clavate setae (Figs 2 & 6); six spinnerets with anterior lateral spinnerets longer than wide (Fig. 9). Legs with clavate setae resembling spines (Figs 3 & 5); leg I strong with femora strong (Fig. 6). Male resembles the female. *Eleleis limpopo* differs from other species of the genus by the strong brown coloration of the carapace and legs (Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020).

Figs 1–3. *Eleleis limpopo*: 1. Female from Irene. 2. Male from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. 3. Female from Irene grassland. (Photos: Peter Webb)

Figs 4–7. *Eleleis Limpopo*: 4. Female habitus dorsal view. 5. Male habitus dorsal view. 6. Female dorsal view (alcohol material). 7. Female ventral view (alcohol material). (Photo: 4–5 Peter Webb. 6–7 Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Gambia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA. Gauteng: Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23), (NCA 2014/2209); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.74); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.21). **Limpopo:** Tuinplaas, Springbokflats (-24.9, 28.73;(NCA 2003/203); (NCA 2003/427) (NCA 2002/750);(NCA 2003/473); (NCA 2003/429); NCA 2003/886); (NCA 2003/829); (NCA 2003/476); (NCA 2003/474); (NCA 2003/475); (NCA 2003/828); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.94,29.87) (NCA 2009/1702). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29) (NCA 2004/1215).

Figs 10–12. *Eleleis limpopo*: 8. Eye pattern. 9. Spinnerets. 10. Male palp (after Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020). 11. Female epigyne (after Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020). 12. Epigyne. (Photos: 8, 9, 12 Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman)

LIFESTYLE

Eleleis limpopo are free-running ground dwellers and they were sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biomes. As part of the Gauteng Grassland Project (Webb & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014) the species was sampled annually since 2012 from grasslands around Pretoria, in Irene, and the Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014).

They are often found under rocks. They immediately move around to try to get under the rock again (Fig. 13). In Irene they were always associated with small red ants running between them. On the Springbok Flats a large number of specimens were sampled from pitfall traps over a period of a year (2001–2002). The males were sampled from September, October to November as well as in June and July. The females were sampled mainly in October. In Irene the species was photographed on 10 occasions – males mainly during June and July and females in April.

Fig. 13. *Eleleis limpopo* female collected from under rocks at Irene in grassland. Photo: Peter Webb

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